

LINGUISTIC FEATURES IN ACHIEVING COHESION: AN EXAMPLE OF JOSEPH EDOKI'S *THE UPWARDS PATH*

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Abstract

This study attempts to explore some linguistic features in Edoki's *The Upward Path*, which are aimed at achieving cohesion in the text. The study investigates the functions of some cohesive devices in the discourse, including conjunctions and reference. Through the adoption of the systemic functional grammar as a model, the research exposes the implications of conjunction, and underscores the place of reference in the text. Some excerpts are obtained from the novel through content analytical approach. The study shows that conjunction plays a vital role in making the plot of the text unified, and reference gives more direction to the readers.

Key words: Discourse, Conjunction, Reference, text

Introduction

This paper analyses the role of some linguistic features in achieving cohesion in the narrative of **Joseph Edoki's** *The Upwards Path*. The study is set to investigate the devices of cohesion in the text, as tools used to expose bad governance, with a view to enhancing good leadership in Nigeria. Therefore, the work explores the novelist's use of dialogue, among the characters that represent government officials, as they communicate and give directives through interaction. All this underscores the linguistic functions of cohesive elements in the text, such as conjunction and reference.

Theoretical Framework

This work adopts Systemic functional grammar to explore the use of cohesion in text, by explaining the grammatic and semantic properties in the text, and accounting for their relationship within a discourse. Michael Halliday and Ruqaiya Hasan state that, "cohesion occurs where the interpretation of some elements in the discourse depends on that of another" (4). He goes further to state that, "it is a set of possibilities that exists in the language for making text hang together: The potential that the speaker or the writer has at his disposal... Thus, cohesion as a process always involves one item pointing to another; whereas, the significant property of the cohesive relation... is the fact that one item provides the source for the interpretation of another" (19). Concisely, cohesive ties have some functions in text. Calvin Nwogu identifies functions of cohesive devices

as: “The means by which we link any form of text or written material together. They help the writer and make the relationship which exists between ideas and sentences clearer to the reader” (32).

Cohesive devices are: (i) conjunction, (ii) reference, (iii) ellipsis, (iv) substitution and (v) lexical organization and they create coherence of any text (Halliday and Hasan, 9). Olga Navratilova expounds that, “coherence is associated primarily with the use of cohesive devices which guide the listeners/readers towards a discourse interpretation intended by the speaker/writer” (134). This study focuses on the first three devices which would be discussed in tandem with views of scholars like (Halliday 603-642, Nwogu, 31-34, Kunle, 70-76, Malmkjaer, 623-25) on cohesion that link textual ideas for better understanding and the study looks at the interpretation of proposition to supposition and visa-vis. It further investigates the use of interrogative sentences (rhetoric) in political discourse.

Reference

This refers to resources for referring to a participant or circumstantial element whose identity is recoverable. We have personal, demonstrative, and comparative reference which can be logically anaphoric (the referent precedes the reference or cataphoric (reference precedes referent)). The followings are types of reference:

Personal reference is reference by means of function in the speech situation, through the category of person like personal pronouns and possessive pronouns. For example, I, me, you, we, us, he, him, she, they, them, and possessive determiners; mine, my, hers, yours, our, his, hers, etc.

Demonstrative reference is reference by means of location on a scale of proximity. It is essentially a form of verbal pointing where a speaker identifies the referent by locating it on a scale of proximity. In a situation where it functions as head, then it shifts to personal pronoun. It consists of determiners; these, this, that, the, and adverb/adjunct; here and there. **Comparative reference** is indirect reference by means of identity or similarity which can either be general comparisons or particular, for examples; (adjectives) same, equal, identical similar, additional, (adverbs) identically, differently, likewise, so much, otherwise, so more less equally etc. (Halliday and Hasan 37-81). “Comparative reference is expressed through adjectives and adverbs and serves to compare items within a text in terms of identity or similarity” (Nunan David 24).

Cohesive Conjunction is an explicit marker of meaning connection between clauses that create semantic linkage in a discourse. This is achieved through additive, adversative, temporal or causal conjunction.

a). **Additive Conjunction.** This item is used to introduce an addition to the erstwhile clause. The most prominent additive Conjunction is “and”. Other examples include, yet, so, further, moreover, among others.

b). **Adversative Conjunction.** This refers to markers which are used to indicate contradiction of ideas. It shows that the proposition expressed in the second clause is contrary to what was stated earlier in the preceding clause. Examples include; but, however, instead, rather, ecetera.

c). **Causal Conjunction.** This helps to create cause and effect relationship in the text. Causal relation is used to show that something led to another thing to happen. It signifies result, purpose or reason for the erstwhile proposition. It is signalled by words, such as so, hence, therefore, consequently, etc.

d). Temporal Conjunction. This is used to show a relation between two successive sentences in sequence of time. This could be sequential (then, next), simultaneous (simultaneously, at the same time), preceding (earlier, previously), immediate (at once, immediately), durative (meanwhile). (Halliday and Hasan, 231-267)

Political Discourse

Political discourse refers to the text produced for political matters. Thus, politics covers large areas. Paul Baylay demonstrates the scope of politics in his definition as all embracing. According to him:

Politics is limited to the activity of the institutions, such as government, parliament and parties, fulfilling their role of distributing resources. To complement this, it could be defined as a struggle for power among the members of these institutions through elections, parties, parliamentary procedures and propaganda. A wider definition would include the activities of those organizations that belong to civil society and which are not necessarily regulated by the state but at the same time compete for resources – trades unions, business associations and environmental groups (3).

In view of the above assertion, this study X-rays politics in simple perspective, which includes media report, government policies and deliberation, as well as academic research. However, the context of the text selected demonstrates politics in power struggle and maintenance. The study of cohesion and interrogation with regard to political discourse plays a significant role in the analysis and understanding of our chosen text. Towards this end, we employ content and syntactic analysis of the selected texts from the perspective of politics.

Textual Analysis

The text addresses the most challenging problem of bad leadership in African countries, but also implies a ray of hope for development. The extract below exposes how African is underdeveloped

Extract 1

1 And how is your project going? I've met with the boss of the National Planning Commission... and what did you get from him? ∞ Lies, ∞ official lies, How? Blatant lies, bogus figures, incredible statistics, garbage,... that is the challenge of working in a developing country... what exactly did the director tell you? The man said there is no poverty in the country- no poverty at all. (8)

In extract 1 above, four interrogatives are found playing information requisition role which allows Mr. Gaga shows his state of dissatisfaction with the data, and moves further for authentication. Other cohesive properties used in the text are clausal ellipsis in line 2, the speaker deletes [the information are]; personal reference 'I' replaces Mr. Gaga creates texture in the discourse. Robinson advises Mr. Gaga to go and justify its authenticity in the village "go to the villages and verify his claim" (9).

Similarly, the extract below reflects the negative effects of international politics on African countries.

Extract 2

No citizen of this country is living below the poverty line. We are the best-fed nation in the world.

The poorest households spend only ten percent of their income on food. Our economy is growing at fifteen percent, ninety percent of the graduates in our country are gainfully employed, over a million of citizen is engaged in research and development, inflation is zero percent (5-6).

The above text reveals that the influence of western ideology on African politics serves as background for Mr Gaga's proposal to conduct in-depth research on one of African country called Savannah. The first data he got from National Planning Commission reveals details of his visit, which he eventually neglects.

Contrary to Western perspective, the information reveals the true colour of the nation. There is personal reference 'our' in lines 2 and 3 determines the head as a specific entity; it is used at pre-modifying position in the nominal group 'our economy, our country' and the use of 'we' in line 1 serves as pronominal reference which tied the text. Also portrayed in the text, is unpopular government policies, which hinder development. The extract below centres on corruption as a great enemy to the development of any country.

Extract 3

Any rich man or woman whose source of wealth cannot be explained is a thief. If we stop honouring them, they will stop stealing (4).

The extract signals a strong emphasis on, accountability in governance in the society, through the use of pronominal references [we], referring to the entire citizens and the government in particular, while [they, them] are employed as corrupt elements in the country. Another cohesion that relates the first event with the second is also causal conjunction [if], that shows conditional relationship.

These cohesive devices establish semantic relation in the text, which makes the communication convincing. The subsequent revelation unveils how the government of Savannah carries out its business both internally and internationally.

From the fore going, it could be observed that corruption and development cannot be simultaneously present because where corruption stands, development disappears and vice-visa. Considering the effect of the former on the later, in its effort to curtail corruption in Savannah, the government made a policy to dent encroachment of corruption. The president used all means to enlighten people on the effect of corruption which in turn moulds and shapes everyone. It becomes popular among members to disgrace any corrupt element, regardless of his influence or position. The government mounts campaign billboards and even in the offices.

The extract below also captures the challenge of foreign domination of African economy.

Extract 4

Our country is different. We earn so much money from the sale of crude but instead of using the foreign currency to import food, we channel the earnings into farming, research, education and industrial development. (48)

The use of adversative conjunction [but] defines what makes it different in one perspective and in another way it stands as divergent view from that of Western leaders who are aiming at imposing their currency's value over Africans. That plan makes the government in question to succeed. The reference [we] stands for the good leaders of Savannah and creates relationship among the different events to act as unified structure. The narrative depicts that the great machinery that is responsible for the formulation, execution and implementation of policies and programmes, that will transform the country into socio-political and economic development, is good governance. One may recall that since the colonial era, the reverse is the case in African societies. This is so because of bad leadership in government, which in turn, affects African economies and subsequently, the nation becomes under-developed.

Through the devices of causal conjunction and adversative, the extract below does not spare the need for a well-defined security architecture in Africa

Extract 5

You were brought here because you were found on the street by 10am-looking this way, that way. What you were doing is very unusual. By ten everybody goes out to work. I know what you want to say. Don't worry; the charge of wandering will not stand because I know you. The day you step into the country, the security agents took notice. When you moved to New Dodokido, it was recorded. When you visited Fingesse and Marantaun, it was noted. But when you came to Merigo City and decided to live here, the security operatives became confused'...Police record has it that, you applied for a job at the University....We know your background – even down to your Rwandan roots!'(153-4)

The above extract represents an interview between Mr. Gaga and Divisional police officer at Wara Ose police station. Mr. Gaga was caught stranded on the street by a constable police officer, who takes advantage of the effective security network system of Savannah to access his complete information including his movements to rescue him. The use of causal conjunction [because] twice, temporal [when] in some clauses to assert the serial occurrence of his action bit-by-bit and adversative [but when], signals the point of suspicion, together with pronominal reference [you] as subject of discussion and [your] possessive reference as well as demonstrative reference [the] that defines the nominal heads in various occasions within the discourse, enclosed all parts of the text logically to create semantic relation of the text and serves as unified whole. However, the extracts below are interrogatives employed to elicit some information.

Extract 6

What is the duration of each plan?... Could you please throw more light on the plans?... What about technological research? (162)

The interrogatives are geared towards getting the necessary information from the appropriate quarters to find useful solution to developmental issues. The subsequent answer reveals the rationale behind the success of the administration in developing the nation.

Similarly, the extract below is pre-occupied with the need for development.

Extract 7

We carried out what we call the national development plan... there is first national development plan, the second, third and so on and so forth.' 'Five years, and we have so far implemented the first two plans.'... 'The development plan involves two principal issues: setting of goals, ordering of priorities. And then there is a time frame. In our country we started with food production and technological research. In the first five years, we spent thirty percent of our annual budget developing five million hectares of farmland, building one million ultra-modern in-farm cottages and bungalows, building asphalt roads in rural communities- all to achieve massive and sustainable food production. By the end of the five years, food prices had fallen to an all-time low... (162-4)

The above extract utilizes temporal conjunctions, '**By the end of the five years**', '**and then**' and '**In the first five years**', each allowing ideas to flow. These conjunctions tied the presuppositions and suppositions in a sequential order and the use of 'in the first five years, in the same five years' functioned as simultaneous cohesive conjunction that connected the whole text. The pronominal reference 'we' is used as the subject to refer to government. Savannah is self dependent because of good planning, which is the secret to the wealth and food sufficiency of the referent country. The extract below deploys comparative conjunction.

Extract 8

A country is as good as the character of its leadership (168)

The extract captures Fernando's words his interactive session with Gaga. The use of comparative conjunction 'as good as' correlates the habits of government officials to tally with character of its citizens. Where government machineries behave decisively, the followers will also comply which gives it success. Again, Gaga puts a question that directly represents Western perception of Africa in the extract below.

Extract 9

What about the view expressed by another famous thinker that "a people deserve the kind of leaders they get"? (168)

The interrogative marks derogatory remarks that reveals divisive thinking of Western world about Africa. This Western ideology had no place in Savannah of the twenty first century. That was why Professor said "if you say Africans deserved the cruel and corrupt leaders they had in the twentieth century, you would have succeeded humoring and insulting the people" (168). Contrary to Western definition, Africa has totally changed to a fresh world with the help of good leaders and mass-centre style of government. The question is thrown to dent coherent system of Africa. The discourse unveils the ideological conflict between Western world and Africa.

Conclusion

The work shows that cohesive properties play effective role in promoting the message of a literary text, whereby characters manipulate their utterances in such a manner to render useful information, and in portraying intended meanings. Accordingly, the cohesive reference and cohesive conjunction coordinate the text, to create stylistic value, which in turn motivates readers or listeners. Following the successful use of the linguistic tools, the text impresses and fascinates not only the readers, but also linguists as well as students, in order to carry out investigation. The work

adequately exposes some African thematic concerns of the electorates and politicians through the devices of cohesive properties in Joseph Edoki's *The Upward Path*, which reveals the atrocities of bad leaders and depicts how good leadership produces dividends of democracy to the society.

Works Cited

Agho, Jude Aigbe and Isaac O. Atere. "The Praxis of Good Governance in Wale Okediran's *The Boys at The Border* and Joseph Edoki's *The Upward Path*." *Lokoja Journal of English and Literature (LOJEL)* Vol. 1, No. 1, 2020

Joseph Edoki. *The Upward Path*. Lagos: Nookia Publishers, 2008. Print.

Halliday, K. Michael and Matthiessen, M. I. M. Christian. *Halliday's Introduction to Functional Grammar*. London: Routledge, 2014. Print.

Halliday A. K. Michel and Ruqaiya Hasan. *Cohesion in English*. London: Longman, 1976, Print

Lena, Kulo. *Linguistic Features in Political Speeches*. Lulea: UP. 2009. Print.

Malmkjaer, Kirsten. *The Linguistic Encyclopedia*. London: Routledge, 2006, Print.

Nunan, David. *Introducing Discourse Analysis*. London: Penguin English, 1993, Print.

Olga, D. Navratilova. et'al *Coherence and Persuasion in Political Speeches: Ideological Coherence in Coherent Discourse*: Masaryk, Coherence and Coherent in English Discourse. Žerotínovo: Masaryk U Press, 2017. Print.

Nwogu, N. Calvin. *Writing Tasks: A Course in Essay, Letter, Summary And Report Writing*. Yola: Paraclete Publishers, 2013. Print.